

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF NUMBERS IN ORAL TRANSLATION IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich is paying attention to improve literature, culture and art greatly: "Speaking about the development of the cultural and humanitarian sphere, first of all, it should be noted that this year 12 imotant documents related to the issues of culture, art and literature were adopted.

ABSTRACT

Language is a communication tool. It is for sure, but the unrepeatable and rincomparable duties of language are not only that. Because, language is the treasury which embodied the history, social-political life, spiritual, philosophical-religious outlook of a nation. These very peculiarities are especially visible in literature.

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Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich is paying attention to improve literature, culture and art greatly: "Speaking about the development of the cultural and humanitarian sphere, first of all, it should be noted that this year 12 imotant documents related to the issues of culture, art and literature were adopted.

In order to increase the role and significance of creative unions in the life of the country, to strengthen their material and technican base, the Public Fund for Support of Creative Persons of Uzbekistan has established and also the Friend clubs, in conjunction with literature, cultural and art institutions, large companies and banks".¹

Translation is a mental activity in which a meaning of given linguistic discourse is rendered from one language to another. It is the act of transferring the linguistic entities from

¹Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and order as well as personal responsibility must a daily rule of every official's daily activities. Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2017.-P.234.

one language in to their equivalents in to another language. Translation is an act through which the content of a text is transferred from the source language in to the target language.

Translation – is the transmission of a language means expressed in another language. It is an important tool, ensuring the fulfillment of communicative function in those cases where people express themselves in different languages and exchange their ideas.

In today's world the question of speed has become even more vital due to the fact of breaking news round the clock. Recently research in mass media has grown so extensively. In the first instance, it was the print media which supplied the basis for critical analysis. Some studies examined the language of the press, highlighting specific lexical, syntactic and stylistic features. Comparative studies revealed differences in the language in quality papers compared to the broadsheets, linking these differences to the specific readership expectations. Translation is considered to be a very important tool in all fields of knowledge, communication and education. It is used to convey and share information between different cultures with different backgrounds and it is 3 considered as a means of communication between people around the world. It gives them the ability to communicate their thoughts, ideas, feelings, cultures and notions. Newmark stated that translation is the rendering of the meaning of a text from the source language into another language (target language) in the same way that the writer intended it. Following his steps, many other researchers investigated and studied this field, such as Lederer who said that translation is the process which is set to establish equivalence between two texts in two different languages. These equivalents depend on three main factors which are the nature of the two texts, their objective, and the relationship between the two cultures involved. In conclusion, translation is a high level writing skill which many find it to be the most difficult skill. It requires that writers and translators must have the ability to express their ideas in the target language as accurate as they would in their mother language. Therefore, the problem of interference emerges when writers and translators try to import linguistic structures of (L1) and force them onto (L2). They also don't realize or comprehend that every language has its own rules and structure and each one expresses ideas in different ways by different means. The relationship between interference and translation is evident and clear in different texts i.e. political. In order to understand the reasons that cause bad translation, we have to investigate interference from the first (L1) in the second language (L2). There won't be any translations without interference as Malkiel believes. He claims that interference would even occur in (L1) and confirms that it is not only a feature of L2 translation. Therefore, this problem should be investigated from both sides in order to get accurate results of its reasons and effects. Many aspects of the number word series have been studied by scientists and linguists. Their features are studied in a number of textbooks, books and scientific works in Russian, English and Uzbek. From the point of view of translation it is also rich in interesting facts and requires exploration.

Numbers also have some difficulties in translation. Of course, numbers are important for language learners, even though they are not significant, but a student or learner who compares English and Uzbek may not notice the difference between them. However, we can see that the English language numbers are significantly different from the Uzbek ones. For the translator's work, a thorough study of them will be useful. The problem with translation of numerical words usually causes problems for translators. At the same time, Minyar-

Beloruchev, who worked in the field of translation methodology of numerical words, also proves that the translation of numerical words has specific difficulties and advises to work hard. Montanell: came in with the sergeant and three guards.

The distinction between the Uzbek count and the English count is that in the syntactic "count from noun to noun", nouns maintain the number of units, for example: two thousand swords, one hundred fares, seven balls, and the semantics of the number represent the numerical characteristics of the subject.²

In English, however, the opposite is true - in such compounds the noun requires a plural form: three guards. Here is a typological difference between the distribution of two markers in one category, namely the plural morpheme in Uzbek and the number mutually rejecting each other. The count shows the total number of subjects. In this case, the form in the Uzbek language is envisaged without affixes. Such numbers are used in numerical words.

The numbers can be used to denote the number of units and the number of distributions. There are no differences between the numbers two and three, and two and three numbers, that is, the numbers, represent the exact number of objects. The meaning of number and distribution is an additional sign of these meanings. Compare the following examples: *The Chairman slaughtered one calf and one sheep*. If we add the affix - ta in the above example to the number of unchecked numbers, we can see that the exact meaning does not change. Therefore, it is advisable to study the numbers labeled in the numbers.

Analysis of the actual material shows that the numbers are used analogically in comparable languages. In English, the use of marking and unmarked numeric forms can be used to express numerical numbers in Uzbek, for example: *You must have two good horses and a cart*. *Bir arava-yu ikkita yaxshi ot kerak*.

The syntactic meanings of the numbers are as follows: a) in the prepositive combination with the detector; b) with the attribution and predicate function of the sentence; c) Substance is easily transferred to another lexico-grammatical classification of words, that is, the function of the sentence changes; d) The Uzbek language was later used as a condition, the consensus quickly becomes paradigmatic, and so on. Count numbers are used in their original way, for example: *The house has been standing here for thirty years* - *Uy bu yerda o'ttiz yildan beri turibdi*.

In this example, counting causes no problems with the translation. Let's take the following statement in Uzbek: *Mening do'stim uchinchi xonada o'tiribdi*. In the first glance, the word *uchinchi* in this sentence is English. We have to translate as following: *My friend is standing in the third room*. But when using the house, books, trams, lessons, etc., the numbers are used and put before the noun. In Uzbek, this number is given.

In summary, the correct translation of the sentence above is as follows: *My friend is sitting room No.4*. Compare: *Flat four - to'rtinchi xonada*, *Bus (number) forty two - 42-avtobus*, *my number is 90 6359096 (nine zero six three nine zero nine six) - nomerim 906359095 me*. In such cases, the word (number) may be dropped. Here is another example: *Uchinchi betdagi mashqni toping*. This statement is based on the above analysis: Open the exercise on page 18. However, there are also translations that sometimes lead to misunderstandings: *Open the exercise on page 18*. Consider another aspect. If the names of people are used with a number,

²Neubert Albrecht. The Impact of Translation on Target Language Discourse Text vs. System. London. 2000.-P. 96-101

the inscription uses the Roman number after the person's name, but the number is read as a number: *One of the kings of England was Henry V (Henry the fifth)*. This is not a problem in translation because it is available in English and Uzbek: *One of the kings of England was Henry V (Henry the Fifth)*.

References:

1. Suprun A.E. The name is numeral and its study at school. Moscow, 1964.
2. Arinstein V.I. The word - the deputy "one" in modern English. Cand. dis. Leningrad, 1996.
3. Shoabdurakhmanov Sh., Askarova M., Xojiev A., Rasulov I., Doniyorov Kh. Hozirgi uzbek adabiy tili (Modern Uzbek Literary Language.). 1 qism, Toshkent, 1980.
4. Zhubotinskaya S.A. Numerals in modern English. Abstract of Cand. thesis. Kiev, 1982
5. Shvachko S.A. Logical and language categories of quantity. Kiev 1981, 96-102 pp.
6. Boronov Zh.B. Comparative typology of English and Turkic languages. Moscow –Vysshaya shkola||, 1983.
7. Fayzullaeva E.M. The typological category of quantitiveness and multilevel means of its equation in the Uzbek and English languages. Abstract. Cand. thesis. Tashkent 1986.
8. Minyar-Beloruhev R.K. Methods of learning to translate by ear. Moscow, 1959, 80-86 pp.9. Асқарова М.А., Саидниёзова Х.М. «Бир» сўзининг қўлланиши ҳақида. Ўзбек тилшунослигининг айрим масалалари. Илмий асарлар. Тошкент, 1972, 42-45 б
9. Birinbaum Ya.G., Kuznetsov I.A. About one use of numerals in modern English. Some questions of English philology. Chelyabinsk, 1969, Issue I, pp. 62-76
10. [10] Nizomiddinov S. The numbers in the present Uzbek language. Tashkent, 1963, 91 p.
11. Bain A.A. First English Grammar, London. 1982, p 47- 61.
12. Blokh M.Y. A Course in Theoretical English Grammar
13. <https://translationexcellence.com/the-challenges-of-translating-numbers-and-math/>
14. ENGLISH - UZBEK TRANSLATION PROCESS AND THEIR ANALYSIS. Abdullayeva Markhabo Raxmonkulovna
15. Problems with Numerical translation in Uzbek and English Mavlyanova Umida Khojakbarivna.
16. www. Researchgate.net English number idioms